

Improvement of Concrete Durability and Strength with Epoxy Resin Concrete

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Suggested Citation

Mridha, N., Zakaria, M., Khan, M.S.R., Rahman, M.M., & Galib, M.O.F. (2024). Improvement of Concrete Durability and Strength with Epoxy Resin Concrete. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2(6), 689-699.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2024.2\(6\).61](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2024.2(6).61)

Abstract:

Portland cement concrete has wide applications in construction owing to its good strength and relatively low cost. However, exposure to extreme environmental conditions has many significant drawbacks. Cracking due to mechanical stresses, chemical degradations, and extreme fluctuations in temperature accelerate the deterioration of concrete by way of loss of strength and increased permeability. One promising solution for these challenges is Epoxy Resin Concrete. ERC uses epoxy resins as binders, which increase its mechanical properties and strength significantly. The high adhesive power, low permeability, and excellent chemical resistance of epoxy

resins create a highly cross-linked structure that significantly improves the toughness and durability of concrete. Consequently, ERC has several superior properties to conventional concrete, such as compressive strength, flexural strength, and crack resistance. It suits ERC in demanding environments, like marine structures, industrial floors, and road engineering. Enhanced performance of the ERC will be highly relevant for increasing the durability and safety of infrastructure subjected to severe conditions. This paper explores the advantages of ERC and its potential to offer a more durable and resilient solution to the challenges of modern construction.

Keywords: epoxy resin concrete, mechanical properties, durability, compressive strength, environmental degradation.

Introduction

Traditionally, cement concrete is generated by mixing Portland cement with fine aggregates, such as sand, coarse aggregates, and water. Their manufacturing consists of some complicated chemical reactions to give tenacity of strength, solidity, elasticity, endurance, and consequently durability to this material, which, among other particularities, possesses high resistivity associated with its reasonably acceptable price and malleability, justifying its diffused utilisation in constructive processes generally. Unfortunately, whenever OPC-based concrete undergoes severe environmental or mechanical

stresses and is even subjected to excessive changes in environmental temperature, such durability, the resulting mechanical strengths significantly decay. In the long term, this leads to the buildup of stresses in the concrete; therefore, it cracks, generally loses strength, and becomes permeable, accelerating further degradation.

Figure 1 compares the compressive strength of the two – between epoxy resin concrete and OPC. Comparison plots on the mechanical properties show both materials' performance to suit changes in environmental conditions. It shows that ERC continuously records a higher compressive strength under harsh ambient

conditions. This testifies to a better durable aspect from a mechanical property point about their counterpart ordinary concrete and its

promising characteristics toward becoming a replacement and alternative for OPC concretes to use in infrastructure.

Figure 1. Comparison Of Compressive Strength for ERC Vs. OPC

Most of the research has been related to epoxy resin concrete (ERC), a polymer-modified concrete that improves mechanical properties and durability. Epoxy resins, known for their excellent adhesion, low permeability, and high chemical resistance, greatly enhance concrete's performance. As a binder, epoxy resins form a highly cross-linked structure, improving the concrete's strength, toughness, and lifespan. ERC has shown better performance in marine structures, industrial floors, and road engineering, where resistance to environmental degradation is crucial (Li et al., 2023; Zhi, 2003). Studies show that ERC significantly increases compressive strength, flexural strength, and crack resistance compared to traditional

concrete. Its reduced permeability prevents harmful chemicals and water infiltration, significantly extending the lifespan of concrete structures exposed to harsh conditions. Moreover, ERC demonstrates exceptional resistance to chemical attacks, including chloride penetration, sulfate damage, and acidic environments (El-Hawary, 2010; Tabatabaeian et al., 2019). Several studies highlight the benefits of ERC over traditional Portland cement concrete (OPC) in terms of compressive strength, flexural strength, and resistance to severe environmental conditions. The table below summarises key findings from recent research comparing ERC and OPC's mechanical properties and environmental resistance.

Table 1. Summary of Key Studies Comparing ERC and Traditional Concrete

Study	Compressive Strength (Increase)	Durability	Environmental Resistance
Ghassemi & Toufigh (2020)	38.7% decrease under acidic conditions	High	Excellent resistance to chemical attacks
Li et al. (2023)	-	High	Resistance to chloride penetration, sulfate attack
Tabatabaeian et al. (2019)	-	Very High	Superior crack resistance and permeability reduction

Despite the many advantages, ERC has a significant limitation in the high cost of epoxy resins, contributing much to the material cost. That confines its use to specialised applications where performance justifies the expense (Li et al., 2023). Besides, the curing process of epoxy resins is sensitive to temperature and humidity, which may cause variability in the final properties of the material. These are overcome through constant research on optimising mix design and reducing the cost of epoxy resins in ERC. Various studies have been done on using alternative fillers, including silica fume and fly ash, for cost reduction of materials, with added value related to the mechanical properties (Tabatabaeian et al., 2019; Zhi, 2003). Innovative resin formulations also have great potential for more economical and practical ERC against various applications. In summary, epoxy resin concrete's mechanical strength, durability, and resistance to environmental degradation are substantially improved. While the high material

cost remains challenging, further research into cost-reduction strategies and performance optimisation is expected to widen its application in high-performance infrastructure.

Research on Epoxy Resins

Epoxy Resin

Epoxy resin, introduced in 1947, is a highly versatile thermosetting polymer widely recognised for its exceptional mechanical properties, chemical resistance, and thermal stability. The defining feature of epoxy resins is the presence of the epoxy group, a reactive three-membered ring structure consisting of two carbon atoms attached to an oxygen atom. This group is responsible for the resin's ability to undergo polymerisation reactions when interacting with curing agents, transforming the resin into a rigid, cross-linked polymer network.

Figure 2. Synthesis of Bisphenol A-type epoxy resin (ASTM D1763-00)

The epoxy group imparts some of the characteristics of epoxy resin to the epoxy resin, including excellent adhesion in a solid state and

minimal shrinkage while curing, with strong bonding on substrates. Its performance and durability depend upon the fact that it bears the

epoxy group, whereby covalent bonds can easily be formed with hardeners such as amines, anhydrides, and polyamines, bringing about the performance and durability of the product under environmental stresses, including changes in temperature, chemicals, and mechanical effects. For this reason, they suit very severe environmental conditions of use, where the materials are subjected to strong chemicals and higher moisture with extreme temperature fluctuations. About concrete, epoxy resins are used as binders in epoxy resin concrete (ERC), which is superior in strength, durability, and chemical resistance to conventional Portland cement concrete. When added to concrete, these resins drastically improve their mechanical properties due to the formation of a dense, cross-linked network that resists crack propagation and enhances bonds between aggregates. The dense molecular structure increases the compressive and tensile strength of the concrete while reducing its porosity and permeability, thus preventing harmful chemicals and water from penetrating. Additionally, the presence of the epoxy group is critical to ERC's resistance against environmental degradation. Strong bonding capability and low resin permeability show excellent resistance against chemical attacks, such as chloride, sulfate, and acid exposure, common causes of deterioration in conventional concrete (Tabatabaieian et al., 2019; Dehoff, 1961). ERC is also resistant to freeze-thaw cycles due to the presence of an epoxy resin matrix, a common issue in cold climates where infiltration by water can cause traditional concrete to crack and degrade over time. Recent developments in the formulation of epoxy resin concern optimising its properties, making it more environmentally sustainable and cost-effective so that it can be rendered accessible for extended applications.

Innovations in bio-based epoxy resins and curing processes are continuously being made to improve epoxy resin concrete's cost-effectiveness and performance (Chen et al., 2013; Kumar et al., 2006).

Curing Agents and Other Additives

The curing agents play an essential role in the performance of epoxy resin concrete due to their possibility to polymerise epoxy resins into a cross-linked network. The type of hardener used will be important to the properties considered crucial for its behaviour: mechanical strength, thermal stability, and chemical resistance. The most commonly used are aliphatic amines, imidazole-based hardeners, anhydrides, and polyphenolic hardeners, differing in curing behaviour and, consequently, in property profile (Xiang & Xiao, 2020). Besides curing agents, many different additives contained in the epoxy resin formulation further enhance and customise these properties. Plasticisers reduce viscosity for improved workability and embrittling by adding toughening effects that improve fracture toughness due to improved impact strength and enhanced flexibility (Chen et al., 2013). Such materials are usually treated with flexibility to enhance performance in dynamic environments by reducing the incidence of cracking under stress. Selection of the proper curing agent and additives will determine whether a correct balance between strength, flexibility, and durability has been struck in the epoxy resin concrete (Strzelec, 2007; Zhang, 2011). ERC can only attain optimal mechanical and chemical resistance performance by optimising the curing agent and additive composition. The best performance suits it for high-performance uses like industrial flooring, pavement engineering, and marine structures (Lei & Cao, 2015; Jin et al., 2015).

Table 2. Curing Agent Types - Advantages, Disadvantages

Curing Agent Type	Advantages	Disadvantages	Reference
Aliphatic Amine Curing Agents	Fast curing at room temperature and heating can improve the product's strength at high temperatures.	Toxicity is high; the curing process is violent, and the cured product is brittle and has poor toughness.	Qi et al., 2023

Aromatic Amine Curing Agents	Better heat resistance and chemical resistance than aliphatic amines	Specific toxicity, low reactivity, requires heating to cure the resin, poor toughness	SeidlovĀj et al., 2023
Anhydride Curing Agents	Stable chemical properties, lower volatility than amine curing agents, good storage stability; excellent heat resistance, electrical properties, and mechanical properties in cured products	Curing agents do not contain active hydrogen and have a slow curing rate. They react with water, require sealed storage, and are poorly resistant to alkali and solvents.	Fauzi et al., 2023
Imidazole Curing Agents	Low cost, low volatility, relatively low toxicity, good thermal stability, and long shelf life	High reactivity, challenging to store, usually solid, poor compatibility with epoxy resin	Chen et al., 2023
Mercapto (Polysulfide) Curing Agents	Fast curing in the presence of a small accelerator can be used in low-temperature environments, is transparent, and has few by-products.	It does not react with epoxy resin without an accelerator, and controlling reactions with improper accelerator dosage is challenging. It also has low bonding strength after curing.	Li et al., 2023
Epoxy-Functionalized Curing Agents (e.g., DOPO-based Curing Agents)	Improved fire safety and mechanical properties reduce peak heat and smoke release during combustion.	The potential for increased brittleness in the resin system may need specific conditions for optimal curing.	He et al., 2023
Polymer and Nanofiber Reinforced Curing Agents	It improves mechanical strength, bonding properties, and crack resistance and reduces water absorption.	Increased complexity in the curing process may affect thermal stability	Gebre et al., 2023

Curing Mechanism and Toughening Methods

Curing happens typically through the reaction of the hardeners and the epoxy groups of resins, turning liquid to thermoset with an emission of heat in an exothermic reaction. The adhesion after curing usually tends to be higher, the tensile strength reaches higher values, and further heat resistance increases. Therefore, the two main mechanisms determining the curing process are anionic and cationic.

- The active species in the anionic mechanism attack the epoxy group, which gives an intermediate accelerating agent that results in the network being more stable and, hence, very minimum shrinkage upon curing.
- The mechanism for this is cationic; the epoxy rings react with proton donors to form bonds and hydroxyl groups, completing the curing. While this method is sensitive to moisture, according to Zhuang et al. 2020, it provides excellent thermal stability.

Among the advantages of these epoxy resins is a higher cross-linking density when cured, hence

attaining leading mechanical properties like higher tensile and compressive strength. On the other hand, the major disadvantage of these cured epoxy resins is embrittlement arising from their structure, which significantly lessens impact resistance. This can be a problem in those applications requiring more flexibility and toughness.

Following are some of the toughening methods developed to overcome these limitations:

- In-situ matrix toughening generally involves dispersion into the epoxy matrix of specific quantities of such materials as elastomeric, thermoplastic, or rigid phases dispersed by physical means acting as tougheners and offering a composite of reinforced epoxy resin that has enhanced resistance during an impact event with higher flexibility. The following modifiers, being thermoplastic and flexible, calculate new characteristics different from the rigid aromatic type for the cross-link network upon addition and might thus bring out improved fracture-resistance properties in such materials.

- Flexible curing-agent toughening is another efficient pathway for improving toughness in an epoxy matrix using flexible curing agents. When subjected to curing, these flexible curing agents provide flexibility owing to flexible segments. As mentioned earlier, the resultant epoxy has more fracture toughness and hence increased ability towards dynamic loading resistance. Testimonials confirm that using nitrile terminated curing agents, even upon low-level modification, resins tend to do pretty remarkably upon impactation (Wang et al., 2020).

These methods are essential for expanding the range of applications for epoxy resin concrete (ERC), allowing it to perform well under mechanical stress and in aggressive environments such as marine structures, industrial flooring, and bridge decks (McGarry & Sultan, 1969; Wang et al., 2020).

Research on Epoxy Resin Concrete

The most used variety of this material is based on epoxy resin, in which the binding material is partially or consists of epoxy resin. The mechanical strength and resistance against chemical attacks of this concrete are immensely enhanced. Besides this, compared to the other kinds of polymer concretes, the performance in tension and flexion obtained for epoxy resin-based concretes is higher in polyester-based and vinyl-ester-based concrete cases. Therefore, it has excellent prospects in this industry sector. This section deals with performance analysis and influential factors of epoxy resin concrete for guidance on preparing and developing high-performance resin concretes.

Porosity

Porosity is one of the most determining factors describing the durability and performance of epoxy resin concrete. Unlike the highly porous traditional Portland cement concrete, epoxy resin concrete reveals much lower porosity due to the evaporation of excess water during its curing process. The epoxy resin fills the voids between aggregates, thus providing a denser and more tightly bonded matrix with fewer air pockets. Thus, ERC has typically recorded a

porosity within the range of 3 to 4%, which is very small compared to conventional concrete porosities of between 9% and 18% (Zhao et al., 2020).

Impact on Durability and Strength

The less porosity in resin concrete contributes to the following:

- To improve durability, adding low porosity to ERC's chemical resistance and imperviousness to water offers better resistance to freeze-thaw cycles and chemical degradation arising from the action of acids and salts (Gong & Li, 2020).
- Higher Strength: A dense matrix means a better load-bearing capacity; the reduced void increases resistance to compression and tension, thus making ERC ready for high-demanding applications, such as bridges and industrial floors (Natarajan et al., 2020).

Factors Affecting Porosity

The porosity of ERC may be influenced by:

- Epoxy Resin Content: Increasing resin content increases the porous structure. However, excess resin application makes the coating brittle (Zhao et al., 2020).
- Curing Conditions: Proper curing is important to achieve low porosity, one of the distinctive features of good quality ERC. Inadequate curing may lead to incomplete cross-linking of resin, thus increasing porosity. (Gong & Li, 2020).
- Aggregative Quality: The grade and type of aggregates used to influence the density of the mix. Well-graded aggregates help lower porosity by tightly fitting together (Tabatabaeian et al., 2019).

Mechanical Strength

Epoxy resin concrete develops superior mechanical properties with high compressive, tensile, and flexural strength compared to conventional Portland cement concrete. These advantages are mainly due to the dense structure developed in ERC, which enhances stability, crack resistance, and toughness to resist impact.

- **Resin Content Effect:** The quantity of epoxy resin plays a vital role in developing an optimum mechanical property in ERC. A literature review of several studies shows that increased resin content has enhanced ERC specimens' compressive, tensile, and flexural strength. Adding the resin up to 12 - 14 wt % has generally resulted in an optimum between tensile and flexural strength of the epoxy-aggregate composite specimens (Gupta et al., 1982). Further increase in the resin content beyond this may result in brittleness. Hence, toughness is reduced (Niaki et al., 2018).
- **Addition of Fillers:** Adding fillers, such as basalt fibres and fly ash, can further increase the strength properties of epoxy resin concrete. For example, adding basalt fibre-reinforced epoxy concretes increases tensile strength by up to 35% and impact strength by up to 315% (Niaki et al., 2022). [Leech, 1992; Nguyen, 2020]. Adding nano clay and MWCNT increased the epoxy composites' compressive and flexural strength. The enhancement in compressive strength had a maximum value of 189.25 MPa. (Nguyen, 2020).
- **Curing Temperature and Hardener Type:** It is reported that curing conditions, including temperature and hardener type, affect the mechanical properties of ERC. Some researchers showed that higher curing temperature enhances strength development; hence, meta-xylene diamine (MXDA) developed the highest compressive and flexural strengths at high temperatures (Jin et al., 2017). This indicates that only an appropriate curing method will maximise the mechanical properties of epoxy resin concrete.
- **Performance under Various Loading Conditions:** Epoxy resin concrete works very effectively under dynamic loading conditions, such as tensile and compressive stresses. ERC has been proven to be more ductile and resilient than conventional concrete under cyclic loading conditions, hence its applications in bridge decks and industrial flooring where high mechanical demand exists. The polymeric binder better distributes stresses across the concrete matrix (Qian et al., 2021).

- **Applications in Aggressive Environments:** The high mechanical properties developed by ERC make it suitable for application in areas that demand great strength and durability, such as marine and chemical exposure (Lokuge & Aravinthan, 2013). Epoxy resin, adding fly ash, improves the compressive and flexural strengths while having high resistance to harsh chemicals. It has a very low porosity, and the resulting binder is highly resistant to corrosive attacks; thus, the resistance to chemical attack shall be good, with no deterioration in epoxy resin cement concrete.

Chemical Corrosion Resistance

Epoxy resin concrete has excellent chemical resistance and is far superior to conventional Portland cement concrete under severe conditions. The dense matrix developed by epoxy resins makes ERC highly resistant to aggressive chemicals, including acids, alkalis, and salts.

Resistance to Acidic and Alkaline Environments

These studies also indicated that epoxy resin concrete does not lose strength and integrity even under sulfuric solid and hydrochloric acid conditions. For example, Golestaneh et al. (2013) reported that ERC showed minute mass loss and strength degradation after a long period of exposure to the acid solution. Hence, it is suitable for applications in seawater structures and wastewater treatments. In the same way, ERC has been found to have excellent resistance in alkali exposure since there was no effect on its compressive strength even in strong alkali solution, as recorded by Ribeiro et al. in 2002.

Resistance to Salt Exposure

ERC also presents excellent chloride-induced corrosion resistance. Tests on saltwater and sodium chloride performed on the ERC degraded significantly less than regular concrete. Thus, ERC suits coastal and marine applications (Ribeiro et al., 2002).

Performance in Abrasive Environments

Apart from chemical resistance, ERC has better abrasion resistance and hence finds a wide range

of applications in industrial floors and pavements where wear and tear are very high. Thus, the combination of chemical resistance and physical durability prolongs the life of concrete under aggressive conditions.

Future Applications and Research Prospects for Epoxy Resin Concrete

Epoxy resin concrete has emerged as a high-performance, advanced material with increasing applications in almost all civil engineering and transportation fields. It can satisfy the changing requirements of construction projects today by mitigating many drawbacks usually seen with traditional Portland cement concrete.

Consequently, several types of epoxy resins, curing agents, and curing procedures affect the performance of concrete. The use of inadequate resin and curing-agent types or concentrations will impede the achievement of mechanical properties and durability by this type of concrete. Further study in future research is undoubtedly being done on the composition and design of performance. Civil engineers will need to interact extensively with polymer material scientists to appreciate how to optimise the properties and applications of these polymers.

Though costly, epoxy resin concrete's excellent mechanical strength, durability, and chemical

resistance make it suitable for applications without traditional materials. For example, Ribeiro et al. showed that due to high demands regarding marine structures and industrial flooring, it is urgent to study the economic performance of epoxy resin concrete mixes in depth.

However, one of the significant obstacles to using epoxy resin concrete is that epoxy resins are thermosetting materials and are not readily recyclable. This infers the environmental question of demolishing and disposing of epoxy resin concrete constructions at the end of their life. Recent studies have focused on renewable epoxy resins used as binders in polymer concrete to reduce such problems. Using bio-based materials, the production process cost for epoxy resin concrete will be reduced by having sustainable and eco-friendly properties without compromising excellent all-round performance and addressing the recyclable issue. As shown in Table 3, while ERC gave Ka an excellent mechanical strength and durability advantage, its high material cost remains one of the limiting factors in the wide-scale adoption of these laser-cut printed circuit boards. Therefore, all the challenges have been tackled proactively by continually researching and developing new material formulations.

Table 3. Summary of Advantages and Challenges of ERC in Research

Study	Advantages	Challenges	Suggested Improvements
Ghassemi & Toufigh (2020).	High compressive strength	High cost of epoxy resin	Use of alternative fillers like silica fume
Li et al. (2023).	High chemical resistance	Expensive material	Improve resin formulations for cost reduction
Tabatabaieian et al. (2019)	Excellent crack resistance	Sensitive curing process	Control curing temperature and humidity

Conclusions

Epoxy resin concrete represents a significant advance over Portland cement concrete due to its unique combination of superior mechanical properties, chemical resistance, and durability. Thermosetting in nature, the three-dimensional crosslinked structure of epoxy resin and its

functional groups is exceptionally thermally stable, adhesive, and resistant to chemical and environmental degradations. Hence, ERC is preferred in severe environmental applications, including marine use, industrial flooring, and chemical processing plants.

Recent advances in toughening techniques, such as in-situ matrix reinforcement and the use of flexible curing agents, have further enhanced the toughness and impact resistance of epoxy resin materials by overcoming one of the most critical limitations of traditional epoxy resins: brittleness under certain conditions. These developments make ERC more viable for structural applications requiring strength and flexibility.

- Epoxy resin concrete possesses good mechanical strength, impermeability, and resistance to chemical corrosion compared to traditional concrete. The factors that will affect the mechanical properties of ERC are mainly the variety of epoxy resin, the selection of curing agents, and the ratio of mixing and curing conditions. Properties like the compression strength, tensile strength, and flexural property of the concrete depend significantly upon the composition and processing parameters of the resin. They must, therefore, be carefully controlled if optimum performance is to be achieved in practice.

- Despite the high price for epoxy resin concrete, the outstanding properties of ERCC justify its use in the relevant applications where conventional Portland cement concrete may be unsatisfactory. The increasing demand for superior performance concretes, particularly critical infrastructure works, including bridges, airport pavements, industrial floors, and so forth, presents a challenge to supplementary ERC formulation and processing to make it less expensive and suitable for more applications.

However, the long-term benefits of these non-recyclable thermosetting resins offset the environmental concerns. There is a need for continuous research on bio-based resins and recyclable polymers over such concerns. Such innovations can go a long way in effectively reducing ERC's environmental impacts while maintaining superior performance.

References

ASTM D1763-00. (2021). *Standard specification for epoxy resins*. ASTM International.

Chen, P., Xu, S., Zhou, X., & Xu, D. (2023). An experimental study on flexural-shear behavior of composite beams in precast frame structures with post-cast epoxy resin concrete. *Buildings*, 13(12), 3137. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13123137>

Chen, Y., Yang, L., Wu, J., Ma, L., Finlow, D., Lin, S., & Song, K. (2013). Thermal and mechanical properties of epoxy resin toughened with epoxidized soybean oil. *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 113, 939–945. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-012-2859-4>

Dehoff, R. (1961). Effect of various curing agents on the chemical stability of epoxy resins. *Corrosion*, 17(1), 83–87. <https://doi.org/10.5006/0010-9312-17.1.83>

El-Hawary, M., & Abdul-Jaleel, A. (2010). Durability assessment of epoxy-modified concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 24, 1523–1528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2010.02.004>

Fauzi, L., Hakim, L., & Simbolon, T. (2023). Manufacturing and characterization of polymer concrete with aggregate from sand, eggshell, and sugarcane waste with epoxy resin binder as sound absorber. *Key Engineering Materials*, 940, 173–181. <https://doi.org/10.4028/p-831153>

Gebre, Y., Lahmer, T., Müller, M., Wiegand, T., Osburg, A., & Tarekegn, A. G. (2023). Properties of concrete with coated aggregates under different loading conditions. *Journal of Research in Engineering and Applied Sciences*, 8(14), 459.

Ghassemi, P., & Toufigh, V. (2020). The durability of epoxy polymer and ordinary cement concrete in aggressive environments. *Construction and Building Materials*, 234, 117887. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.11.7887>

Golestaneh, M., Najafpour, G., Amini, G., Beygi, M., & Noshirvani, B. (2013). Evaluation of chemical resistance of polymer concrete in corrosive environments. *Iranica Journal of Energy and Environment*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.5829/idosi.ijee.2013.04.03.19>

- Gong, J., & Li, K. (2020). Minimizing drying shrinkage and enhancing impermeability of foam concrete modified with epoxy resin. *Advances in Civil Engineering*, 2020, 8897687. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8897687>
- Gupta, A., Kar, B., & Mani, P. (1982). Effect of binder content and coupling agents on mechanical properties of epoxy-aggregate composites. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, 1, 370–377. <https://doi.org/10.1177/073168448200100406>
- He, P., Wang, C., Zhang, Q., Liu, J., & Lu, H. (2023). Performance of concrete with recycled epoxy plate waste as a partial replacement for fine aggregates. *Materiale Plastice*, 23(1), 5643.
- Jin, F., Li, X., & Park, S. (2015). Synthesis and application of epoxy resins: A review. *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, 29, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiec.2015.03.026>
- Jin, N., Yeon, J., Seung, I., & Yeon, K. (2017). Effects of curing temperature and hardener type on the mechanical properties of bisphenol F-type epoxy resin concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 156, 933–943. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2017.09.053>
- Kumar, S. A., Balakrishnan, T., Alagar, M., & Denchev, Z. (2006). Development and characterization of silicone/phosphorus modified epoxy materials and their application as anticorrosion and antifouling coatings. *Progress in Organic Coatings*, 55, 207–217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.porgcoat.2005.10.001>
- Lei, Y., & Cao, X. (2015). Preparation of epoxy-resin concrete using microwave curing method and its pavement performance evaluation. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 27(5), 04014221. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)MT.1943-5533.0001179](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)MT.1943-5533.0001179)
- Li, S., Cui, H., Wang, H., Wang, W., Sui, Y., Dong, L., & Wang, J. (2023). Preparation and performance investigation of epoxy resin-based permeable concrete containing ceramsite. *Polymers*, 15(24), 4704. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15244704>
- Li, Z., Liu, A., Gao, D., Wu, C., Liu, X., & Zhai, H. (2023). Mechanical performance and strengthening mechanism of polymer concretes reinforced with carbon nanofiber and epoxy resin. *Coatings*, 13(11), 1964. <https://doi.org/10.3390/coatings13111964>
- Lokuge, W., & Aravinthan, T. (2013). Mechanical properties of polymer concrete with different types of resin. *Materials & Design*, 51, 175–181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2013.03.078>
- McGarry, F. J., & Sultan, J. N. (1969). Toughening of glassy crosslinked polymer with elastomeric inclusions. *Civil Engineering Dept., MIT*.
- Natarajan, R., Kumar, P., & Rajendran, S. (2020). Performance enhancement of epoxy resin concrete using polymeric additives. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 21, 2255–2260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2019.08.279>
- Nguyen, T. (2020). Mechanical and flame-retardant properties of nanocomposite based on epoxy resin combined with epoxidized linseed oil. *Journal of Chemistry*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/2353827>
- Niaki, M. H., Fereidoon, A., & Ghorbanzadeh Ahangari, M. (2018). Mechanical properties of epoxy/basalt polymer concrete: Experimental and analytical study. *Structural Concrete*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1002/suco.201700003>
- Qi, Q., Gao, S., & Xu, P. (2023). The application of recycled epoxy plastic sheets waste to replace concrete in urban construction and building. *Processes*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr11020397>
- Qian, Y., Li, Z., Jin, Y., & Wang, R. (2021). Experimental study on axial tension members of a new epoxy resin concrete. *Science of Advanced Materials*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.1166/sam.2021.4133>
- Ribeiro, M., Tavares, C. M. L., & Ferreira, A. (2002). Chemical resistance of epoxy and polyester polymer concrete to acids and salts. *Journal of Polymer Engineering*, 22, 27–44. <https://doi.org/10.1515/polymeng.2002.22.1.27>

Seidlová, M., Hodul, J., Žižková, N., & Borg, R. (2023). Possibilities of influencing the crystallization process of bisphenol A- and bisphenol F-based epoxy resins used for hydrophobic coatings on concrete. *Polymers*, 15(19), 3871. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym15193871>

Strzelec, K. (2007). Studies on the properties of epoxy resins cured with polythiourethanes. *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 27, 92–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijadhadh.2006.02.001>

Tabatabaeian, M., Khaloo, A., & Khaloo, H. (2019). An innovative high-performance pervious concrete with polyester and epoxy resins. *Construction and Building Materials*, 228, 116820. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.11.6820>

Wang, X., Liu, Y., & Zhao, Y. (2020). Impact resistance and fracture toughness of toughened epoxy resin systems: A review. *Polymer Engineering & Science*, 60(1), 100–115. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pen.25237>

Zhang, J. (2009). Study on influence of curing agent on water resistance of epoxy resin. *China Adhesives*.

Zhang, Y. (2011). Study phenolic modified amine's properties with low viscosity for epoxy resin curing agent. *Thermosetting Resin*.

Zhao, S., Guo, X., & Yang, L. (2020). Effect of epoxy resin on the mechanical properties and durability of concrete. *Construction and Building Materials*, 233, 117289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2019.11.7289>

Zhi, L. (2003). The influence of fillers on the mechanical properties of epoxy resin concrete. *Thermosetting Resin*.

Zhuang, G., Chen, Z., & Wei, J. (2020). Experimental study on the micromorphology and strength formation mechanism of epoxy asphalt during the curing reaction. *Applied Sciences*, 10(7), 2610. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10072610>